

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 17

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The goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will align with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 17

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 17:0 A Prayer of David.</p>	<p>Psa. 17:1 תְּפִלָּה לְדָוִד שְׁמֵעָה</p>
<p>Psa. 17:1 Hear a just cause, O LORD, give heed to my cry;</p>	<p>יְהוָה אֲזַדְקֵךְ הַקְשִׁיבָה רִנָּתִי</p>
<p>Give ear to my prayer, which is not from deceitful lips.</p>	<p>הָאֲזִינָה תְּפִלָּתִי בְּלֹא שִׁבְתִּי</p>
<p>² Let my judgment come forth from Your presence;</p>	<p>מִרְמָה : ² מִלְּפָנֶיךָ מִשְׁפָּטִי יֵצֵא</p>
<p>Let Your eyes look with equity.</p>	<p>עֵינֶיךָ תִּחְזֶנְנָה מִיִּשְׁרָיִם : ³</p>
<p>³ You have tried my heart;</p>	<p>בְּחִנּוּת לִבִּי אֶפְקַדְתָּ לִילָה</p>
<p>You have visited <i>me</i> by night;</p>	<p>צָרַבְתָּנִי בַל־תִּמְצָא זְמֹתִי בַל־</p>
<p>You have tested me and You find nothing;</p>	<p>יַעֲבֹר־פִּי : ⁴ לִפְעֻלֹת אָדָם</p>
<p>I have purposed that my mouth will not transgress.</p>	<p>בְּדַבַּר שִׁבְתֶּיךָ אֲנִי שָׁמַרְתִּי</p>
<p>⁴ As for the deeds of men, by the word of Your lips</p>	<p>אֲרַחֲוֹת פְּרִיץ : ⁵ תִּמְךָ אֲשַׁרִּי</p>
<p>I have kept from the paths of the violent.</p>	<p>בְּמַעַגְלוֹתֶיךָ בַל־נִמְוָטוּ בְּעַמִּי :</p>
<p>⁵ My steps have held fast to Your paths.</p>	<p>⁶ אֲנִי־קָרָאתֶיךָ כִּי־תַעֲנֵנִי אֵל</p>
<p>My feet have not slipped.</p>	<p>הַט־אֲזַנְךָ לִי שְׁמַע אִמְרָתִי : ⁷</p>
<p>Psa. 17:6 I have called upon You, for You will answer me, O God;</p>	<p>תְּפִלָּה תִּסְדְּרֶיךָ מוֹשִׁיעַ חוֹסִים</p>
<p>Incline Your ear to me, hear my speech.</p>	<p>מִמֶּתְקוֹמָמִים בְּיַמִּינֶךָ : ⁸</p>
<p>⁷ Wondrously show Your lovingkindness,</p>	<p>שְׁמַרְנִי כְּאִישׁוֹן בַּת־עַיִן בְּצֹל</p>
<p>O Savior of those who take refuge at Your right hand</p>	<p>כְּנֶפֶךָ תִּסְתִּירֵנִי : ⁹ מִפָּנֵי</p>
<p>From those who rise up <i>against them</i>.</p>	<p>רָשָׁעִים זֶו שָׁדוֹנִי אִבִּי בְּנֶפֶשׁ</p>
<p>⁸ Keep me as the apple of the eye; Hide me in the shadow of Your wings</p>	<p>יִקְיֹפוּ עָלָי : ¹⁰ תִּלְבַּמוּ סָגְרוּ</p>
<p>⁹ From the wicked who despoil me,</p>	<p>פְּיָמוּ דַבְּרוּ בִּגְאוֹת : ¹¹ אֲשַׁר־יִנוּ</p>
	<p>עַתָּה סִבְבוּנִי [סִבְבוּנִי] עֵינֵיהֶם</p>

My deadly enemies who surround me.

¹⁰ They have closed their unfeeling heart,

With their mouth they speak proudly.

¹¹ They have now surrounded us in our steps;

They set their eyes to cast us down to the ground.

¹² He is like a lion that is eager to tear,

And as a young lion lurking in hiding places.

Psa. 17:13 Arise, O LORD, confront him, bring him low;

Deliver my soul from the wicked with Your sword,

¹⁴ From men with Your hand, O LORD,

From men of the world, whose portion is in *this* life,

And whose belly You fill with Your treasure;

They are satisfied with children, And leave their abundance to their babes.

¹⁵ As for me, I shall behold Your face in righteousness;

I will be satisfied with Your likeness when I awake.

יִשְׂתּוּ לְנִטּוֹת בְּאַרְצִי : ¹² דְּמִיִּנּוּ

בְּאַרְיֵה יִכְסֹף לְטָרוֹף וְכִכְפִּיר

יֵשֵׁב בְּמִסְתָּרִים : ¹³ קוֹמָה יְהוָה

קִדְמָה בְּנֵי הַכְרִיעָהוּ פִּלְטָה

נִפְשֵׁי מִרְשָׁע חֲרָבָה : ¹⁴ מִמֹּתֵי

יָדָךְ אִיהוָה מִמֹּתֵי מוֹחֶלֶד

חֲלָקָם בְּחַיִּים וְצָפִינָךְ

[וְ] [צָפוֹנָךְ] תִּמְלֵא בְטָנָם

יִשְׂבְּעוּ בָנִים וְהַנִּיחוּ יְתָרָם

לְעוֹלָלֵיהֶם : ¹⁵ אֲנִי בְצַדִּיק

אֶתְנֶה פָנֶיךָ אֲשַׁבְּעָה בְּהַקְיִין

תִּמְוִנָתְךָ :

Targum

Psa. 17:1 A prayer of David. Accept, O LORD, my entreaty; in righteousness hear my praise; you will incline your ear to my prayer, since my lips are without guile. ² From your presence my judgment shall come forth; your eyes will behold, honesty. ³ You have tested my heart; you have visited me at night; you have purified me [and] not found corruption. [If] I thought of evil, it has not passed my mouth. ⁴ Truly, you have rebuked the deeds of the sons of men by the word of your lips; I have kept [myself from] the ways of audacity. ⁵ Support my steps in your path, lest my feet be shaken. ⁶ I have called you because you will receive my prayer, O God; incline your ear, receive my prayer. ⁷ Display your goodness, O redeemer of those who hope; from those who rise up against them by your right hand. ⁸ Guard me like the circle that is in the middle of the eye; in the shadow of your presence you will hide me. ⁹ From the presence of the wicked, those who harm me; my enemies, in the desire of their soul, surround me. ¹⁰ Their wealth has increased, their fat covers [them], their mouth has spoken arrogantly. ¹¹ Our steps now have surrounded us; their eyes are fixed to extend throughout the land. ¹² He resembles a lion who yearns to tear, or a jungle-cat that dwells in secret places. ¹³ Arise, O LORD, forestall him, strike him down; deliver my soul from the wicked man who deserves death by your sword. ¹⁴ And the righteous who hand over their souls on your account, O LORD, to death in the land, their portion is in eternal life, and their bellies will be filled with your good store; children will be satisfied, and they will leave their surplus to their children. ¹⁵ I in truth will see your countenance, I will be satisfied at the time that I awake, from the glory of your face.

Superscript

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
Psa. 17:0 A Prayer of David.	תְּפִלָּה לַיהוָה

Verse Analysis

This Psalm is called a prayer of David. However, it is a kind of self-evaluation, the search for proper understanding before the LORD. In Psalm 16:8, David praised the lessons that occurred during the dark times in his life. This Psalm describes one of those lessons. David has come to an understanding of the difference between the righteous and their adversaries.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

A self-evaluation before the LORD by David.

Verse One

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 17:1 Hear a just cause, O LORD, give heed to my cry; Give ear to my prayer, which is not from deceitful lips.</p>	<p>שְׁמַעַתָּה יְהוָה צְדָקַת הַקְּשִׁיבָה רִנָּתִי הֲאֲנִינָה תִּפְלְתִי בְּלֹא שִׁבְתִּי מִרְמָה :</p>

Verse Analysis

צְדָקַת (tzdek) – means "righteous." The NASB 1995 offers the translation as "just cause." The word means a condition of human affairs that is ideal to the LORD. Every human should want to live a life that is pleasing unto the LORD.

רִנָּתִי (reenati) – means "cry." This word indicates a great and profound inner agitation that is invoked by joy or sadness.

David offers this prayer to the LORD, hoping that the LORD will hear his prayer. It was an honest prayer of David's condition (of his soul) when he wrote it.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Hear my thoughts of righteousness from my emotions, for I offer this prayer with the truth on my lips.

Verse Two

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>² Let my judgment come forth from Your presence; Let Your eyes look with equity.</p>	<p>מִלְפָּנֶיךָ מוֹשְׁפָטִי יֵצֵא עֵינֶיךָ תִּתְּנֶנָּה מִיִּשְׁרָיִם :</p>

Verse Analysis

Judgment comes from the Sefirot Gevurah. David is praying to Gevurah to offer judgment. Thus, the slate would be cleared.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

May the Sefirot Gevurah offer my judgment, for she will judge me fairly.

Verse Three

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>³ You have tried my heart; You have visited <i>me</i> by night; You have tested me and You find nothing; I have purposed that my mouth will not transgress.</p>	<p>³ בַּחֲנֹתַי לְבִי אֶפְקְדָה לַיְלָה צָרַפְתָּנִי בַל־תִּמְצָא זְמוֹתַי בַּל־ יֵעַבְרֶנִּי כִּי :</p>

Verse Analysis

David acknowledges that the judgment sent from Gevurah upon him was necessary as a punishment for the evil things that he did. David knows that the examination was not just of his actions but also of what was in his heart.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

You have tested my heart at night; You have removed all evil from my thoughts and body so that now I am entirely cleansed and that I would not speak any evil.

Verse Four

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁴ As for the deeds of men, by the word of Your lips I have kept from the paths of the violent.</p>	<p>לְפַעֲלֹת אָדָם בְּדַבַּר שְׂפָתַיךָ אֲנִי שָׁמַרְתִּי אֶרְתֹּת פְּרִיץ :</p>

Verse Analysis

Crimes committed against neighbors serve to bring the deeds of humans under the sovereignty of the LORD's Law to become lessons for the people who wish to be righteous. Thus evil serves the purposes of righteousness, and the criminal unwittingly advances the cause of the LORD's kingdom on earth.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The deeds of the wicked are lessons to the righteous as to how not to behave.

Verse Five

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁵ My steps have held fast to Your paths. My feet have not slipped.</p>	<p>⁵ תִּמְנֹךְ אֲשֶׁרִי בְּמַעַנְלוֹתֶיךָ בִּלְ- נִמְוֹטוֹ בְּעַמִּי :</p>

Verse Analysis

David understood that his suffering was to become a source of strength. He asked the LORD to keep his word and actions within the bounds that the LORD's Law has drawn. The precepts of the Torah must be followed as one moves forward through their life.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

My word and actions have been within the boundaries defined by your Torah.

Verse Six

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>. Psa. 17:6 I have called upon You, for You will answer me, O God; Incline Your ear to me, hear my speech.</p>	<p>אָנִי־קָרָאתִיךָ כִּי־תַעֲנֵנִי אֱלֹהִים־ אֲזַנְךָ לִי שְׁמַע אִמְרֹתַי : 7</p>

Verse Analysis

David calls out to the LORD the same way a child cries out for its mother at night. The child cries out to hear the mother's voice reassuring the child that he/she is not alone. David calls to the LORD in the same manner. He needed to feel that the Shekinah was still with him.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

LORD may your Shekinah assure me that You are still with me.

Verse Seven

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁷ Wondrously show Your lovingkindness, O Savior of those who take refuge at Your right hand From those who rise up <i>against</i> them.</p>	<p>הַפְּלִיָּה תִסְדֵּד מוֹשִׁיעַ תּוֹסִים לְמַתְקוֹמְמִים בְּיַמִּינְךָ :</p>

Verse Analysis

One result from suffering is that the LORD offer a path to moral perfection to those who wish it through Your forgiveness. The righteous persons of this world demonstrate the trust that exists between the LORD and humanity.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Let Chesed shine forth, a help to all who trust in You because You save all who ask for it.

Verse Eight

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
8 Keep me as the apple of the eye; Hide me in the shadow of Your wings	שְׁמֵרֵנִי כְּאֵי שֹׁן בַּת-עַיִן בְּצִלֵּי כְּנָפֶיךָ תַּסְתִּירֵנִי :

Verse Analysis

בַּת-עַיִן (bat – eyin) – literally means "daughter of my eye." This phrase is an idiom for the expression "apple of the eye." A better translation for the idiom is "the eyelid protects the eye." David was asking for the LORD's help to steer him away from the moral decay and evil in the world.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Keep me from entering into anything immoral by hiding it from me.

Verse Nine

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
9 From the wicked who despoil me, My deadly enemies who surround me.	9 מִפְּנֵי רָשָׁעִים נָי שָׂדֵינִי אֵיבֵי בְּנֶפֶשׁ יִקְיֹפוּ עָלַי :

Verse Analysis

David has lost every material possession that he had. He believed that his enemies were now going to steal his soul.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The wicked who took all my possession are now are coming after my soul.

Verse Ten

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹⁰ They have closed their unfeeling heart, With their mouth they speak proudly.</p>	<p>¹⁰ תָּלַבְמוּ סִגְרוּ אֲיִמוּ דְבָרוֹ בְּגִאוֹת :</p>

Verse Analysis

The Hebrew does not contain the word for "heart." A better translation is, "They have well hidden that which they cherish most, so they say proudly with their lips." David was talking about his enemies' precious possessions.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

They have well hidden that which they cherish most, so they say proudly with their lips.

Verse Eleven

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹¹ They have now surrounded us in our steps; They set their eyes to cast <i>us</i> down to the ground.</p>	<p>¹¹ אֲשֶׁר־יָנוּ עָפְתָה סְבִיבוֹנֵי [סְבִיבוֹנֵי] עֵינֵיהֶם יִשְׁתּוּ לְנִטּוֹת בְּאֶרֶץ</p>

Verse Analysis

David asks why his enemies hate his way of righteous living. He felt they were leading him astray from the ways of the LORD. His enemies stole his material possessions, and their present actions are directed at his way of life.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

They hate our righteous living, so they try to make us stray from the right path on earth.

Verse Twelve

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹² He is like a lion that is eager to tear, And as a young lion lurking in hiding places.</p>	<p>¹² דָּמֵינּוּ פֶּאֶרְיָה יִכְסֹף לְטָרוֹף וְכִפִּיר יֵשֵׁב בְּמִסְתָּרִים :</p>

Verse Analysis

The enemy is ready to tear David apart like a young lion who lurks waiting for its prey.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

He waits like a lion, ready to tear me apart.

Verse Thirteen

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 17:13 Arise, O LORD, confront him, bring him low; Deliver my soul from the wicked with Your sword,</p>	<p>13 קוּמָה יְהוָה קְדָמָה בְּנִי תִּכְרִיעֵהוּ פִּלְטָה נַפְשִׁי מִרָשָׁע תִּרְבֵּד :</p>

Verse Analysis

David pleads with the LORD to confront his enemy and stop the wicked plan. In many places in the Hebrew Scriptures, the LORD is envisioned as a triumphant warrior with a sword.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Arise LORD and stop my enemy so my soul will not fall victim to him by using your sword.

Verse Fourteen

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹⁴ From men with Your hand, O LORD, From men of the world, whose portion is in <i>this</i> life, And whose belly You fill with Your treasure; They are satisfied with children, And leave their abundance to their babes.</p>	<p>14 מְמַתִּים יָדְךָ אִתְּהָה מְמַתִּים מִחֶלֶד חֶלְקָם בְּתַיִם וְצִפְיֶיךָ [וְ] [צִפְוִנְךָ] תְּמַלֵּא בְטֶנֶם יִשְׂבְּעוּ בָנִים וְהֵנִיחוּ אֶתְרָם לְעוֹלָמֵיהֶם :</p>

Verse Analysis

מְמַתִּים (mem'tim) – means "men" or "people." It denotes people of only passing importance.

וְצִפְיֶיךָ [וְ] [צִפְוִנְךָ] תְּמַלֵּא בְטֶנֶם (vutz'peen'cha [vu] [tz'pun'cha] t'male veet'nas) – this phrase refers to the joy to be enjoyed by the righteous people in the world to come. This joy is spiritual. Wicked people see this as something that they can steal in the physical world. They do not understand that the joy from the LORD will be available only spiritually.

It is a request to allow the wicked to believe that it is best to have all their material desires filled in this lifetime. They will not be looking for anything in the world to come. Through their actions, they will not inherit the world to come. Let them have plenty of children to leave their material wealth to because that will be their legacy.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

From the men who are Your tools, O LORD; from the men of transitory import whose portion is in this life, and whose stomachs You fill with that which is hidden – let them have children in plenty and let them leave their abundance to their offspring.

Verse

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹⁵ As for me, I shall behold Your face in righteousness; I will be satisfied with Your likeness when I awake.</p>	<p>¹⁵ אֲנִי בְצֶדֶק אֶתְהַוֶּה פְּנֵיךָ אֲשַׁבֵּעַה בְּהַקְיִץ הַמְּוִנְתֶּךָ :</p>

Verse Analysis

David acknowledges that it is the spiritual joy in the world to come that is most important.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

As for me, I will live in thoughts of righteousness, and one day I will awaken in your spiritual presence, and I look forward to that day.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

A self-evaluation before the LORD by David.

Hear my thoughts of righteousness from my emotions, for I offer this prayer with the truth on my lips.

May the Sefirot Gevurah offer my judgment, for she will judge me fairly.

You have tested my heart at night; You have removed all evil from my thoughts and body so that now I am entirely cleansed and that I would not speak any evil.

The deeds of the wicked are lessons to the righteous as to how not to behave.

My word and actions have been within the boundaries defined by your Torah.

LORD may your Shekinah assure me that You are still with me.

Let Chesed shine forth, a help to all who trust in You because You save all who ask for it.

Keep me from entering into anything immoral by hiding it from me.

The wicked who took all my possession are now are coming after my soul.

They have well hidden that which they cherish most, so they say proudly with their lips.

They hate our righteous living, so they try to make us stray from the right path on earth.

He waits like a lion, ready to tear me apart.

Arise LORD and stop my enemy so my soul will not fall victim to him by using your sword.

From the men who are Your tools, O LORD; from the men of transitory import whose portion is in this life, and whose stomachs You fill with that which is hidden – let them have children in plenty and let them leave their abundance to their offspring.

As for me, I will live in thoughts of righteousness, and one day I will awaken in your spiritual presence, and I look forward to that day.

Appendix

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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